

PRAGMA-STYLISTIC FEATURES OF TIME PERCEPTION IN THE FRAMEWORK OF LITERARY TEXT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10159847>

Abstract. *The focus of the research article is on the principles of pragma-stylistic language elements and how crucial they are for expressing time in literary texts. Writing fascinating and engrossing stories requires the ability to express time in literary texts through these pragma-stylistic elements. These elements can provide the reader a stronger feeling of time and a more intense sensory experience. Effective use of the pragma-stylistic features allows authors to create truly captivating stories that keep readers hooked from beginning to end. This article therefore will explore each of these features and discuss their role in expressing time in literary text.*

Keywords: *pragma-stylistic features, literary texts, significance, elements, time, mood: pleasant or negative, voice: first-person and third-person, temporal adverbs, tense: present, past, future, aspects: length, conclusion, continuance.*

Аннотация. *В центре внимания исследовательской статьи находятся принципы прагмо-стилистических языковых элементов и то, насколько они важны для выражения времени в художественных текстах. Написание увлекательных и увлекательных рассказов требует умения выражать время в художественных текстах с помощью этих прагмо-стилистических элементов. Эти элементы могут дать читателю более сильное ощущение времени и более интенсивный сенсорный опыт. Эффективное использование прагмо-стилистических особенностей позволяет авторам создавать по-настоящему увлекательные истории, которые держат читателей на крючке от начала и до конца. Поэтому в этой статье мы рассмотрим каждую из этих особенностей и обсудим их роль в выражении времени в художественном тексте.*

Ключевые слова: *прагмо-стилистические элементы, художественные тексты, значение, элементы, время, настроение: положительное или отрицательное, залог: первого и третьего лица, временные наречия, время: настоящее, прошедшее, будущее, аспекты: объем, заключение, продолжение.*

Annotatsiya. *Tadqiqot maqolasida asosiy e'tibor tilning pragma-stilistik elementlari tamoyillari va ularning badiiy matnlarda vaqtni ifodalashda qanchalik muhim ekanligiga qaratilgan. Qiziqarli va jozibali hikoyalar yozish uchun badiiy matnlarda vaqtni ushbu pragma-stilistik elementlar orqali ifodalash qobiliyati talab etiladi. Ushbu elementlar o'quvchiga kuchliroq vaqt hissi va kuchliroq hissiy tajribani taqdim etishi mumkin. Pragma-stilistik xususiyatlardan samarali foydalanish mualliflarga o'quvchilarni boshidan oxirigacha qiziqtiradigan haqiqatan ham jozibali hikoyalar yaratishga imkon beradi. Shuning uchun ushbu maqola ushbu xususiyatlarning har birini o'rganadi va ularning badiiy matnda vaqtni ifodalashdagi rolini muhokama qiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *pragma-stilistik xususiyatlar, badiiy matnlar, ahamiyat, elementlar, vaqt, kayfiyat: yoqimli yoki inkor, ovoz: birinchi va uchinchi shaxs, zamon qo'shimchalari, zamon: hozirgi, o'tmish, kelajak, aspektlar: hajm, xulosa, davom.*

Introduction

Literary texts are genuine works of art that are expertly crafted by writers. The way literary works represent time is just one of the numerous factors that make them exquisite. Time can be a tricky thing to convey and is a significant factor in shaping the meaning, the plot and character development of literary texts. Pragmo-stylistic features of language are the elements in writing that contribute to the style and meaning of the text. One of the important aspects of pragmo-stylistic features is the expression of time in literary text. Different writers use different techniques to express time in their writing, and this helps to create different literary styles that readers can appreciate and engage with [1, p. 2-3]. Pragmo-stylistics is also a linguistic approach that examines how language is used in different contexts to achieve specific purposes. It examines the relationship between language and society, and how language is used to convey social identity, social distance, and social power. In literary texts, pragmo-stylistics can be used to examine how authors use language to create specific effects and convey particular meanings [1, p. 4-5].

In this article, we will explore the ways in which time is expressed in literary texts through the use of pragmo-stylistic features of language, examining their origins and meanings and the contexts in which they are commonly used.

Materials

It is clear that academicians have not given much consideration to the ways in which pragmo-stylistic elements have been used in literary texts that represent time. Nevertheless, a few studies have been written concerning them. For example, in “The Use of Tense and Aspect in English Fiction” by Louise Sylvester: She analyzes the pragmatic and aesthetic roles of tense and aspect in English fiction. As it may be utilised to represent the chronological framework of a narrative and influence the reader's interpretation of events, she contends that the choice of tense and aspect is a crucial component of literary style. Marcin Grygiel's "The Pragmatic Use of Tense in Narrative Fiction" also explores the practical and aesthetic functions of tension in narrative storytelling. He demonstrates how authors may employ multiple tenses to emphasise the present or past nature of events, construct narrative distance or immediacy, and stress the agency of various characters, among other narrative consequences. Also, "The Pragmatics of Literary Tense" by Richard Walsh: he explores the pragmatic uses of tense in literary texts, making the case that it may be used to construct various degrees of narrative immediacy and distance, as well as various methods of delivering information and narrational styles. [2, p. 24]. It could be stated that the pragmo-stylistic principles and their function in representing time in literary works are covered in all of these topics.

Methods

In this study, the data is organized under pragmatic stylistic features as suggested by Alina Villalva and Richard Walsh in their “Toward a Pragma-Stylistic Analysis of Temporal Expressions in English Fiction” and “The Pragmatics of Literary Tense” respectively. Sarwet Rasul's conceptions in her ‘Pragmo-Stylistic features as an interpretative tool’ were also used to organize the data [1, p. 1-15]. So, it is crucial to communicate time in literary texts since the current study analyses pragmatic elements in a descriptive and interpretive manner. It bases its rules on the presumption that the writers' primary means of expressing time is through the use of pragmo-stylistic components.

Results

To start with, the analysis showed that the pragmo-stylistic features are the main source of ideal in expressing time in literary texts. Despite the fact that academics 'Louise Sylvester', 'Marcin

Grygiel', and 'Richard Walsh' have studied this topic extensively, the unambiguous representations of pragmo-stylistic aspects with instances and data were not covered. Because of this, the next chapter will go in details on the key concepts related to these elements.

Discussion

The significance of representing time in literary works cannot be overstated, it must be said. The advancement of a story's storyline depends heavily on time. Time is a tool that writers use to build tension, surprise, and mystery into their stories. Writers can achieve the tone they want for their work by adjusting the order and length of occurrences [3, p. 5-6]. The representation of time in literary works may also aid in the growth and perspective-shaping of characters. Through the representation of a character's experiences and interactions with other characters across time, a writer can use time to demonstrate character development, maturation, or deterioration. For instance, because to their experiences through time, a character who begins as a shy and self-conscious individual may change into a more confident and aggressive person by the story's conclusion [4, p. 3]. Furthermore, the writer can more effectively convey their desired topic by using pragmo-stylistic qualities to describe time. A writer may make their text have several meanings and interpretations by employing the proper tools. The sense of transience, permanence, or even the cyclical nature of existence may all be expressed via the manifestation of time. Writers may depict the passage of time and how it affects people, places, and events via their writing [5, p. 6]. The way time is expressed in literary works may also add a feeling of reality and authenticity to the narrative. Writers may convey the scene vividly and convincingly by employing specific details, and they can aid the reader in fully engrossing themselves in the narrative by appropriately portraying time. For instance, it is crucial to appropriately portray time while writing historical fiction since it increases the story's authenticity [6, p. 2-6].

When it comes to writing fiction, poetry, or any other form of literature, time is a crucial component that helps to convey a tale and keep the reader engaged. Time may be expressed in literary texts in a variety of ways employing a variety of pragmo-stylistic language qualities. Tense, aspect, mood, voice, and temporal adverbs are some of these characteristics. Each of these elements will be examined in this paragraph along with how they are used to portray time in literary works.

The time when an action or occurrence takes place is referred to as the tense. In literary texts, tense is used to provide a feeling of time and highlight how the many plot points are connected. The past, present, and future are the three primary tenses. Different tenses can be used in literary texts to denote temporal changes, flashbacks, or foreshadowing. For instance, a writer may use the present tense to describe a current situation and create tension while using the past tense to describe events that happened in the distant past [7, p. 4]. Another linguistic device used to illustrate the interrelationships between the events in a tale is the aspect. The length, conclusion, or continuance of an activity are all considered aspects. Simple, progressive, perfect, and perfect progressive are the four categories. They may, for instance, use the ideal aspect to demonstrate how a previous occurrence is essential to the present circumstance or the progressive aspect to denote a drawn-out action that is developing tension [8, p. 6-9]. The attitude or feeling that a writer expresses via their writing is referred to as mood. In addition to indicating a sense of time, such as nostalgia or anticipation, mood can be either pleasant or negative. Readers may feel different emotions depending on the atmosphere, such as suspense, dread, or delight [9, p. 5]. Also, the

point of view from which a tale is conveyed is referred to as voice. The two primary voice tenses are first-person and third-person.

[10, p. 4-9]. And finally, in literary text, writers may use temporal adverbs to indicate a shift in time, to create suspense and anticipation, or to create a sense of nostalgia or regret. The words that denote time are called temporal adverbs. They are helpful in literary texts because they provide the reader a feeling of time and contribute to a richer sensory experience. Temporal adverbs comprise the words "yesterday," "tomorrow," "now," and "later." [11, p. 8].

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is evident that pragmo-stylistic language qualities are crucial for accurately representing time in literary texts. Time is a key component of literature and plays a critical role in the development of characters, the storyline, and the meaning of literary works. In order to develop diverse literary styles that readers can understand and connect with, writers employ a variety of time-expression approaches in their work. Writers may convey their desired subject clearly and engender a feeling of reality in their work by appropriately conveying time. In the end, the way time is expressed in literary works gives the narrative more depth and significance while also improving the reader's reading experience. Time may be portrayed in literary texts using a variety of pragmo-stylistic linguistic elements. Tense, aspect, mood, voice, and the usage of adverbs and verb tenses are some of these aspects.

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